

(CASE REPORT)

Successful application of Yoga Prana Vidya Protocols to normalize Kidney function: A case study of stage 2 kidney disease

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World Journal of Biology Pharmacy and Health Sciences, 2022, 10(01), 001-007

Publication history: Received on 26 January 2022; revised on 30 March 2022; accepted on 01 April 2022

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjbphs.2022.10.1.0062>

Abstract

Introduction: kidneys filter blood by removing waste and extra water to make urine. The kidney's filtration rate, called the glomerular filtration rate (GFR), shows how well the kidneys are filtering. Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD) is known to be the 6th fastest growing cause of death globally. Early detection of CKD can help to protect kidney function. This paper presents a case of Stage 2 Kidney disease treated successfully by the application of Yoga Prana Vidya healing protocols.

Method: This study uses case study method, analysing patient medical records and YPV protocols used in treating the patient for 6 months. Patient feedback also obtained for analysis.

Results: Improvements in the main parameters achieved at the end of 6 months of YPV intervention show that eGFR improved from 79 to 95. Total Cholesterol improved from 235 mg/dl to 165 mg/dl. HDL Cholesterol increased from 32 mg/dl to 47 mg/dl and LDL Cholesterol reduced from 150 mg/dl to 94 mg/dl. Patient achieved peace and satisfaction of YPV treatment that worked for normalizing his kidney condition.

Conclusion: Using the YPV intervention for this patient, only YPV healing was given and no other form of therapy or treatment was given for stage 2 kidney ailment, which shows that YPV Healing System can be applied not only as complementary treatment but also as an alternative treatment mode in such cases of diseases. Further research may be conducted with wider applications of YPV Healing system to various other kidney ailments.

Keywords: Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD); Yoga Prana Vidya System ®; YPV ®; Energy Healing; Complementary Medicine; Alternative Medicine

1. Introduction

1.1. Kidney Disease

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is progressive loss in kidney function over months or years, and when kidney function falls below a certain point it is called kidney failure [1]. CKD is known to be the 6th fastest growing cause of death and estimated deaths globally due to acute kidney injury (AKI) are around 1.7 million annually. Early detection and treatment can often help kidney disease from getting worse. The other option when a kidney fails is Kidney transplant which is very costly and also difficult to get appropriate donor. CKD risk factors include having: diabetes, high blood

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pressure, being overweight, and Family history of kidney failure. the increase in the prevalence of chronic kidney disease (CKD) progressing to end-stage renal disease (ESRD) and the consequent financial burden of renal replacement therapy (RRT) in both developed as well as developing nations has highlighted the importance of CKD and its risk factors [2].

1.2. eGFR (Estimated Glomerular Filtration Rate)

Kidneys filter blood by removing waste and extra water to make urine. The kidney's filtration rate, called the glomerular filtration rate (GFR), shows how well the kidneys are filtering. Those who may have chronic kidney disease (CKD) can take steps needed to protect their kidney function when it is found early.

Testing for GFR can be a complicated and lengthy procedure, and doctors use a formula to estimate GFR known as eGFR. Accurate estimates of the GFR (eGFR) are important for identifying kidney disease, which often has no symptoms until just before the kidneys fail. The standard way to estimate GFR is with a simple blood test that measures creatinine levels. Creatinine is a waste product from the digestion of dietary protein and the normal breakdown of muscle tissue. Aside from CKD, creatinine levels can be affected by other factors, including diet, muscle mass, malnutrition, and other chronic illnesses [3].

1.3. Normal eGFR Number related to age

In adults, the normal eGFR number is more than 90. eGFR declines with age, even in people without kidney disease. See Table 1 below for average estimated eGFR based on age [2].

Table 1 Normal eGFR values vs. age

Age (years)	Average eGFR
20–29	116
30–39	107
40–49	99
50–59	93
60–69	85
70+	75

1.4. Stages of chronic kidney disease

According to the National Kidney Foundation (USA), there are 5 stages of kidney disease as shown below: [2]

- Stage 1 with normal or high GFR (GFR > 90 mL/min)
- Stage 2 Mild CKD (GFR = 60-89 mL/min)
- Stage 3 A Moderate CKD (GFR = 45-59 mL/min)
- Stage 3 B Moderate CKD (GFR = 30-44 mL/min)
- Stage 4 Severe CKD (GFR = 15-29 mL/min)
- Stage 5 End Stage CKD (GFR <15 mL/min)

Generally, CKD of stages 1 & 2 are treatable and manageable without getting worse.

1.5. Yoga Prana Vidya System of treatment & Healing

Yoga Prana Vidya is an integrated and holistic system of complementary and alternative medicine used in the treatment of physical and mental illnesses. It is based on Pranic energy, also known as bio-plasmic energy principle, and is a no-touch no-drug treatment modality. Yoga Prana Vidya system deals with healing the energy body, and which in turn heals the physical body through systematic healing protocols and techniques besides patient self-practice tools such as physical exercises, Rhythmic breathing, forgiveness sadhana, and Planetary peace meditation. The energy body, also known as *Pranamayakosa*, interpenetrates and extends beyond (surrounds) the physical body as shown in Figures 1 and 2, and consists of an inner aura, an outer aura and health rays connecting the inner aura and the outer auras. By comparing the figures 1 and 2, one can visualize the difference in the energy body of a sick person in contrast to the

energy body of a healthy person. The energy body consists of energy centers or chakrams (wheels) as shown in Fig 4, and “Nadi”s (channels) to distribute the energy to various chakrams and body parts. Figure 3 illustrates a picture of the energy body obtained from a GDV (Gas Discharge Visualisation) camera. From Fig 3 we can see the effects of YPV energy healing that removes the defects in the energy body, thereby treating the physical body parts. Trained and certified healers practice the skills of scanning the wheels (energy centres) and aura, and carry out cleansing and energizing the wheels and affected body parts of the sick person. Patients usually experience recovery and relief from illness within a few healings given by the healer. Depending upon an individual’s health condition, a healing session may last for 10 to 20 minutes, and one or more sessions per day as decided appropriately by the healer.

Thus, YPV system uses ancient techniques of energy healing and its protocols are structured for systematic healing of patients for treating various illnesses. More than 30 published research articles show consistent results of recovery for patients. For example, illnesses successfully dealt with by YPV system and documented publications include difficult medical cases [4], cases of type 2 diabetes [5], arterial heart block case [6], post-herpetic neuralgia [7], exostosis of ear [8], and vision improvements [9]. A case of sustained self-healing to lower high blood cholesterol and curing of asthma was achieved by a trained healer [10]. Other published literature includes - Improved wellbeing and immunity achieved with intensive one-month practice [11], cases of first-aid and emergency [12], speedy recovery of COVID-19 patients [13], hypothyroidism [14], serious snakebite [15]. Some interventional studies successfully conducted by Yoga Prana Vidya researchers include, reduction in anxiety and depression of corporate employees [16], improved wellbeing and reduced criminal attitude of under-trial prisoners [17], improvement of IQ and social behaviour of mentally retarded children [18]. One study on improvement of academic performance by the use of Planetary Peace Meditation, of over 100 high school students was also among the published literature [19]. A conference paper of over 400 documented COVID-19 patients healed resulting in speedy recovery successfully was presented and is taken for publication in a scientific Journal [20].

Figure 1 Energy body of a healthy person

Figure 2 Energy body of a sick person

Figure 3 Picture of the energy body taken using GDV Camera

Figure 4 Chakrams (wheels) in the energy body

2. Method

2.1. Case Report

2.1.1. Patient background

The patient was a 58 years old retired defence person residing in Bangalore, India. The Patient has been having blood pressure for more than 20 years for which he has been taking medicine (Valent 80 tablet) for the same. For the past one year he has been taking Olmesartan- 40 mg and metoprolol -25 mg. His Blood pressure was found erratic.

During the 6-monthly regular check up on blood parameters, on 07 June 21, it was found that the patient's Glomerular Function Rate (GFR) was 79 which is categorised as mild decrease in kidney function. According to National Kidney Foundation (USA), average GFR rate for the age group 50 to 59 is 93 ml/Min [3]. The patient was found to have a family history of kidney failure. His mother had died due to chronic Renal failure. Patient was advised for low-salt diet, but no medication was given.

2.1.2. YPV Intervention

From 08 June 21 Yoga Prana Vidya healing was started and the patient was given healing every day initially for 4 weeks. From then onwards, alternate day healing was given. The following Yoga Prana vidya techniques were applied for healing the patient.

- Standard YPV psychotherapy to bring down stress, anxiety and panic.
- Cleansing the environment, food and belongings with divine energy to maintain etheric hygiene.

- Blood strengthening /Purification.
- Internal organ cleansing.
- Regeneration of kidneys
- Hypertension protocol

The above YPV protocols were given for 6 months. A blood test was done after 6 months on 25 January '22 from which The Glomerular Filtration Rate (GFR) was found to be 95, an increase of 16 % and now the kidneys were functioning normally. It is noted that during the YPV intervention for this patient, only YPV healing was given and no other form of therapy or treatment was given for kidney ailment.

3. Results

Improvements in the main parameters achieved at the end of 6 months of YPV intervention for this patient is given Table 2 below.

Table 2 Summary of Lab reports: Improvements in the main parameters of the patient

Parameter	Date 7 June, 2021	Date 25 January, 2022	(Reference)
eGFR	79 ml/Min	95 ml/Min	(93)
Creatinine	1.04 mg/dl	0.88 mg/dl	(0.6 - 1.1)
Total Cholesterol	235 mg/dl	165 mg/dl	(<200)
HDL	32 mg/dl	47 mg/dl	(40 - 60)
LDL	150 mg/dl	94 mg/dl	(<100)

It shows how effectively the YPV protocols and healings helped the patient to improve and normalise the parameters and risk factors related to kidney function, avoiding kidney disease.

4. Discussion

With the YPV techniques adopted it was observed that other blood parameters namely cholesterol, uric acid and creatinine were also normalised. This establishes the holistic nature of YPV. During the course of treatment, the patient felt relaxed, could do all his normal activities without anxiety or physical discomfort.

According to Agarwal and Srivastava [2], CKD is a problem of epidemic proportions in India, and with an increasing diabetes burden, hypertension, and growing elderly population it is going to increase even further. Managing the patient population of CKD even with better organization of RRT (Renal Replacement Therapy) will be impossible [2]. The time, effort and money invested in establishing a prevention program for CKD is definitely going to give results in years to come and ultimately in the long run will still be cost-effective. In a country like India, screening of high-risk individuals for CKD and the risk factors is the simplest and best option.

5. Conclusion

Yoga Prana Vidya System has been acknowledged by thousands of users and patients for providing such a potent energy healing system to mankind at low cost and ease of application, to alleviate the pain and suffering. Using the YPV intervention for this patient, YPV healing only was given and no other form of therapy or treatment was given for stage 2 kidney ailment in this case, which shows that YPV Healing System can be applied not only as complementary treatment but also as an alternative treatment mode in such cases of diseases. Further research may be conducted with wider applications of YPV Healing system to various other kidney ailments.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to express sincere thanks to the patient for sharing medical information pertaining to this case, and also gratefully acknowledge permission given by Sri Ramana Trust to use their copyright terms Yoga Prana Vidya System ® and YPV ®.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent of the patient was obtained for this case report.

Funding

None.

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